

Vehicle Accident Detection Using Arduino UNO

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Abstract

Overall, the aim of the paper is to detect the place where our Vehicle got accident through GPS. Many of them still occur as a result of accidents nowadays. This is a result of specific human activity. Technology has made life easier for us every day. Some actions include driving while intoxicated, driving too fast, disobeying traffic laws, etc. If our vehicle is involved in an accident, the global positioning system (GSM) module will result in sending an alert to our phone number, allowing us to quickly get there and potentially save their lives. In this project, we want to prevent accidents from taking lives. In this paper, we provide a detailed explanation of the components we used, including the Arduino UNO. This project can be developed in the ensuing years. Solving issues of this nature will be the focus of our paper. To lessen the accident, our administration took a number of actions. They had installed specific monitors in the signal that could detect the vehicle's speed and issue a fine.

Keywords : Arduino UNO, GSM module, GPS module.

INTRODUCTION

Some of the technologies under examination also use machine learning methods for better accident prediction and detection. These systems include benefits such as accurate vehicle tracking, quicker emergency service response times, and faster identification and notification of accidents. High installation costs, false positives and false negatives in accident detection, and potential privacy issues with vehicle tracking are some of these systems' drawbacks. Furthermore, elements like network coverage and the accessibility of local emergency services affect how effective these systems are. Overall, there are many accidents and injuries are occurred due to Vehicle accident with the development and use of vehicle monitoring, accident detection, and notification systems. To overcome these constraints and make these systems more dependable and cost-effective, however, ongoing upgrades and breakthroughs in technology and communication protocols are required. Nowadays, everyone uses a car, which may lead to a lot of accidents. More people are dying in our nation as a result of inadequate emergency facilities. We've installed a GPS in the car so that when we can find it, it will immediately send a message to the rescue crew. It is impossible to overestimate the significance of transportation to human civilization, and the vehicle plays a major role in contemporary transportation. But it's impossible to overlook the dangers of driving, particularly in terms of collisions. Speed is a major risk factor when driving, as it not only influences the seriousness of collision the chance of something happening to getting in one. The number

Received: 24 May 2023

Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted 29 June 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8103364>

of fatal accidents has been drastically reduced thanks to the efforts of our government. The traffic laws now contain a huge number of rules and regulations. According to the level of violence, the fee was raised. The minimum fine for driving without a helmet was 1000 rupees. The primary location of a significant accident is where the traffic police have multiple cameras stationed. The camera will measure the car's speed, and if it is too high, it will scan the licence plate and send the appropriate fine to the owner of the offending vehicle. Many foreign nations have these laws in place. The first time it was used was in Tamil Nadu. A step towards strengthening emergency services and lowering the risks to human life linked with traffic hazards and road accidents is the implementation of an automatic alert device for car accidents, as outlined in the article. The system is built to swiftly identify accidents and provide basic data, such as the accident's location, time, and angle, to the nearest first aid facility. The rescue team then receives this information, which may help to save important lives. The technology uses a GSM module and a GPS module, respectively, to send the alarm message and locate the accident. Additionally, the system accurately detects the existence of an accident and the angle at which the automobile rolls over using both vibration sensors and MEMS sensors. Additionally, system has a switch that may be used to stop delivering messages when there are no casualties, saving the medical personnel valuable time. Every nation should place a high focus on enhancing emergency services and lowering traffic dangers and collisions. Technology, like the automatic alert system for car accidents, may offer a practical and efficient answer to this issue. Despite the numerous initiatives worldwide actions performed by governmental and non-governmental groups to increase awareness about irresponsible driving, accidents continue to happen frequently and frequently end in fatalities. If emergency personnel had been able to get to the scene of the accident in time, lives might have been spared in many situations. According to research, a sizable portion of fatalities would have been avoided if emergency assistance had been available sooner. This has led to an urgent need for an efficient automatic accident detection system that can notify emergency personnel immediately and disclose the location of the accident. By offering prompt aid, this system may contribute to saving priceless human lives. It is essential to have a system that can quickly and accurately detect accidents and alert emergency personnel. By doing this, it will be much easier to save lives and less likely that an accident will have a negative effect on people's lives or society as a whole.

Problem statement

Accidents on the road can be fatal and result in extensive property damage. Accident victims frequently can't contact for assistance right away. Therefore, a system that can distinguish accidents and automatically warn emergency services is needed. The goal of an accident detection and alarm system is to develop a system that can accurately identify accidents, assess the accident's severity, and instantly alert emergency personnel so they can render aid as soon as feasible. The system must be dependable, capable of real-time accident detection, and able to function under a variety of environmental factors, including weather and lighting. The objective is to speed up the accident response process.

Scope of the paper

Received: 24 May 2023

Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted 29 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8103364>

Accidents happen randomly and at any time, resulting in considerable property damage and, more crucially, the loss of human lives. In this project, we want to create a system for detecting accidents and alerting emergency services so they can provide prompt assistance. We'll be using the Arduino UNO platform. The project's objective is to develop a system that can detect accidents, notify the appropriate emergency services of their location and severity. The technology can be applied in a variety of settings to increase security and prevent accidents, including factories, workplaces, and construction sites.

Hardware components

A power source, an accelerometer, a GPS module, a GSM module, and an Arduino UNO board are among the hardware elements of the system. An accident may be indicated by sudden variations in acceleration, which are measured by the accelerometer. The GPS module is used to locate the accident, while the GSM module is utilised to send SMS notifications to emergency personnel.

Software components

An Arduino sketch that takes information from the GPS and accelerometer modules and uses the GSM module to deliver SMS messages is one of the system's software components. Additionally, a smartphone application that may receive notifications of accidents and show their location and severity will be created.

Testing and evaluation

To determine how well the system works at spotting accidents, we will test it in a variety of settings, including a moving car, a manufacturing facility, and a construction site. Additionally, we'll assess how well the system identified the accident's location and level of seriousness. A useful use of Arduino UNO in the sphere of safety and security is the accident detection system since it has a large potential to save lives and prevent injuries. The system's precision and dependability, which can be increased through testing and assessment, will be crucial to the project's success. Additional sensors can be added, and the mobile application's functionality can be improved, to further improve the system.

METHODOLOGY

The accident detection and message system was created to be installed in an automobile, like an ambulance or police car. Accident detection and notification are accomplished by the system using GSM and GPS technology. The GPS will locate the accident location, and emergency services are notified via GSM. An Arduino is utilised to operate the device, and an LCD is employed to display accident data. Overall, the method is straightforward and effective, relying on currently available technology to identify and report incidents in real-time.

HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

Received: 24 May 2023

Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted 29 June 2023

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1. ARDUINO

The Arduino UNO is a well-known open-source microcontroller board developed by Arduino.cc and based on the ATmega328P CPU. The Arduino UNO acts as the primary control component in this project, detecting accidents and alerting users. It is in charge of gathering information from a variety of sensors, including vibration sensors, GPRS and GSM modules, and either presenting the outcomes on a display system or communicating them via message. The vibration sensor is crucial to this project's success. It serves as an accident detection module and takes in the vibrations of the vehicle. When an accident is identified, the Arduino gathers data from every other module and uses the GSM module to deliver a message to the receiver. This makes it possible to get real-time accident notifications and take prompt action. Overall, the Arduino acts as the hub for coordinating the numerous sensors and modules, resulting in a dependable and effective accident detection and reporting system. It is a highly adaptive and accessible option for projects of a similar sort due to its open-source nature and widespread usage.

2. GSM MODULE

The GSM SIM900 module is recommended for communication between the GPS, GSM, and the specified mobile number. The PCS 1900 MHz, the DCS 1800 MHz, and the EGSM 900 MHz frequencies are all covered by the tri-band SIM900 module, which runs in the 900MHz to 1900MHz frequency range. For communication with the mobile phone, the transmitting pin of the GPS module and the reception pin of the GSM module are both used. This makes it the perfect option for accident detection and alert systems because it enables the real-time broadcast of location information and emergency messages.

Received: 24 May 2023

Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted: 29 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8103364>

3. GPS MODULE

The SIM28ML GPS module is utilised in this instance to locate the car. The GPS module works by dividing the globe into coordinates, which enables it to precisely track the position of the car. The SIM28ML transmits position information in real time using the NMEA format at a frequency of 1575.42 MHz. This location information is retrieved by the GPS receiver and transmitted to the Arduino for additional processing. Following processing of the location data, it is sent via the GSM module to the saved contacts, enabling emergency services and family members to be informed of the accident's location in real-time. Overall, this system's utilisation of GPS technology is crucial for providing precise and prompt emergency responses.

4. NODE MCU

The Node MCU is an open-source development board made to make IoT (Internet of Things) applications rapidly and effortlessly. It is built on the ESP8266 microcontroller, which has Wi-Fi functionality and can connect to a Wi-Fi network, making it the perfect board for Internet of Things applications that need wireless access. The ESP8266, a USB-serial converter, and a voltage regulator are all included in the Node MCU, which is essentially a low-cost, all-in-one platform. As a result, programmers may easily create and test their Internet of Things (IoT) applications without the need for a separate programmer, voltage regulator, or USB-to-serial adapter. Support for the Lua programming language, a compact, high-level scripting language, is one of the Node MCU's primary characteristics. In order to get started with IoT development, beginners no longer need to learn difficult programming languages. Developers may utilise the enormous selection of Arduino libraries because the Node MCU can also be programmed using the well-known Arduino IDE. All things considered, the Node MCU is a fantastic development board for Internet of Things (IoT) projects that need wireless connectivity. It provides a perfect balance of features, simplicity, and affordability.

5. LCD DISPLAY

In this project, numerals, alphabets, and special characters are displayed on a 16x2 alphanumeric LCD (Liquid Crystal Display) module. The module can display up to 32 characters at once and contains 16 columns and 2 rows. Using the LCD's higher bit data lines, pins 11, 12, 13, and 14, which are connected to the Arduino's digital pins 8, 9, and 10 in 4-bit mode, the module is connected to the platform. The LCD's RS (Register Select) and E (Enable) pins are linked to pins 12 and 13, respectively, on the Arduino. To determine if the data being delivered to the LCD is a command or data, utilise the RS pin. whereas the LCD's ability to read incoming data is enabled by the E pin. The read/write (R/W) pin must be connected to ground in order to write data to the LCD. This shows that the data is being written to the LCD. In conclusion, the LCD module is used to show pertinent details about the accident, like the position and time, and is controlled by the Arduino by using a number of pins.

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Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted 29 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

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Flow chart

A technology called an accident detection and alert system tracks how a car behaves on the road and looks for potential collisions. The system is often made up of a number of sensors, such as cameras, gyroscopes, and accelerometers, which gather information on the movement, speed, and direction of the vehicle. The system can use this data to find trends, including abrupt speed changes, swerving, or braking, that point to a higher chance of an accident. When an accident is identified, the system sends alerts to the driver, any nearby vehicles, and emergency services, including vital details like the accident's location and severity. A collision can be avoided or its severity reduced by autonomous emergency braking or steering systems, which are included with some accident detection and alert systems. An accident detection and alert system has many advantages. These technologies can assist in preventing accidents from happening or reducing the severity of accidents that do occur by giving drivers real-time information about prospective accidents. Additionally, they can speed up emergency services' reaction times considerably, possibly saving lives. Making an accident detection and alarm system accurate, dependable, and compatible with various vehicle kinds are obstacles that must be overcome. But given the potential advantages of this technology, it warrants significant study and advancement in the field of traffic safety.

RESULT

The success of an accident detection and warning system can be evaluated based on its dependability, speed, and efficiency in lowering reaction times to accidents, as well as its capacity to reliably detect accidents and transmit aid requests. To assess the system's performance, many scenarios and settings can be examined, including as various weather and lighting conditions, different speeds, and various accident kinds. By contrasting the system's findings with actual accidents and examining false positives and false negatives, the accuracy of the system may be assessed. The effectiveness of the system can also be assessed by comparing the system's reaction timings against response times following accidents. In order to learn more about the system's usability and usability, surveys of user satisfaction and feedback can also be done. Overall, the effectiveness of an accident detection and alarm system depends on its capacity to promptly dispatch aid requests and accurately identify incidents, both of which have the potential to save lives and lessen the effects of accidents on other road users.

PROPOSED METHOD

A combination of sensors, including a GPS and an accelerometer, is the suggested approach for an accident detection and alarm system. These sensors can be used to detect collisions or unexpected external changes in a vehicle's speed. The driver or occupants of the vehicle are given the chance to cancel the warning if it was a false alarm by using the data from these sensors to initiate one. A request for assistance is sent to emergency services and any listed family members or contacts if the alert is not cancelled or if the user clicks the "Call Help" button. This approach attempts to speed up response to accidents and increase all-around road user safety.

Received: 24 May 2023

Revised: 12 June 2023

Final Accepted 29 June 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8103364>

OBJECTIVE

The goal of the Arduino UNO-based automobile accident detection system is to create a dependable and accurate system that can identify accidents and alert emergency services for quick assistance. The method aims to increase traffic safety and reduce the number of accidents-related injuries and fatalities. The system can detect abrupt changes in acceleration and locate the accident by making use of the capabilities of the Arduino UNO and sensors like accelerometers and GPS modules. In order to facilitate quick and efficient responses, the system can then transmit notifications to emergency services that include the accident's location and level of seriousness. The project's ultimate goal is to create a system that can save lives, stop injuries, and make all roadways safer for everyone.

CONCLUSION

A vital piece of technology that might lessen the severity of accidents on the road is an accident detection and alert system. This system tracks a vehicle's behaviour and looks for potential collisions using a variety of sensors and communication technologies. The technology notifies the driver and/or emergency services when an accident is detected, giving them vital information including the accident's location and severity. With the help of this technology, emergency services can respond much more quickly, perhaps saving lives. The potential advantages of this technology cannot be understated, even if there are a number of difficulties in building an accident detection and alert system, including guaranteeing accuracy, dependability, and compatibility with various types of cars. Implementing an accident detection and alarm system can be a vital step in enhancing road safety and lowering fatalities due to the rising frequency of incidents on the road.

REFERENCES

1. Automatic Traffic Accident Detection and Alert System International Journal Technology Exploration and Learning (IJTEL), Volume 1, Issue 1, (August 2012).
2. J. White, C. Thompson, H. Turner, B. Dougherty, and D. C. Schmidt, "Wreckwatch: Automatic traffic accident detection and notification with smartphones," *Mobile Networks and Applications*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 285-303, 2011.
3. Kommineni Rakesh: Vehicle Tracking and Accident Alert System, National Institute of Technology Rourkela, (2014).
4. H. M. Ali and Z. S. Alwan, "Car accident detection and notification system using smartphone". LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing Saarbrücken, 2017
5. Dr.C K Gomathy, V Geetha ,T N V Siddartha, M Sandeep , B Srinivasa Srujay Article: Web Service Composition In A Digitalized Health Care Environment For Effective Communications, Published by

International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET) Volume 5 Issue 4, April 2016, ISSN: 2278 1323.

6. DR.C.K.Gomathy , V.Geetha , S.Madhumitha , S.Sangeetha , R.Vishnupriya Article: A Secure With Efficient Data Transaction In Cloud Service, Published by International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET) Volume 5 Issue 4, March 2016, ISSN: 2278 1323.

7. V. Pavitra, P. V. Rao, M. D. Gagana, and D. Samanta, Internet of Things (iot): An Assessment, 2015

8. D. Samanta, M. Shivamurthaiah, P. Kumar, D. Umesh, and K. Siddalingappa, Wireless sensor networks model for monitoring system based on iot, Solid State Technology, 2020.

9. A. S. A. Bakar, G. K. Shan, G. L. Ta, and R. A. Karim, lot|eye Drowsiness Detection System by Using Intel Edison with GPS Navigation, pp. 485493, 2018.

10. Y. Ed-Doughmi, N. Idrissi, and Y. Hbali, Real-time system for driver fatigue detection based on a recurrent neuronal network, Journal of Imaging, vol. 6, no. 3, p. 8, 2020.

11. G. Turan and S. Gupta, Road accidents prevention system using drivers drowsiness detection, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering Technology, 2013.

12. Y. Zhang, F. Weninger, and B. Schuller, Cross-domain classification of drowsiness in speech: the case of alcohol intoxication and sleep deprivation, in Interspeech 2017, pp. 31523156, IEEE, 2017.

13. Helia Mamdouhi, Sabira Khatun, Javed Zarrin, Bluetooth Wireless monitoring, Managing and Control for inter vehicle in vehicular adhoc networks, Journal of computer Science, Science Publication; 2009

14. Accident detection and reporting system using gps and gsm module by waleed mohy eldeen ibrahem momen yaseen fadel almola ahmed musab yahia merghani hassan tawfiq hassan supervisor dr.abuagla babiker mohammed babiker october 2017

15. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) ISSN: 2278-3075, Volume-8 Issue-4S2 March, 2019 Accident Detection and Alert System T Kalyani, S Monika, B Naresh, Mahendra Vucha.